

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.20657794

An Assessment of the Nexus between Money Supply and Economic Growth in Nigeria (1981-2022)

Stanley Oghenenyerhovwo Oniovosa¹, Ikechukwu Uchebenu², Prof. Peter Chukwuyen Egbon³ and Prof. Callister Kidochukwu Obi⁴

¹Delta State College of Education, Mosogar, Delta State, Nigeria.

²University of Delta Agbor, Delta State, Nigeria.

^{3,4}Delta State University, Abraka, Delta State, Nigeria.

¹ oniivosastanley@descoem.edu.ng or stanleyoniivososa@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

This study examines the relationship between money supply and economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2018 with the application of the cointegration and error correction mechanism (ECM) in a multiple regression framework. The ADF test results showed that all the series were stationary at first difference, this means the series RGDP, M2, CPS and GEX were integrated at order one I(1) while the cointegration test results revealed that Money supply (M2), Credit to Private Sector (CPS) and Total Government Expenditure (GEX) have long run significant link on Real Gross Domestic Product (RGDP) in Nigeria. The results of the short-run estimation reveal that money supply and total government expenditure have a direct and significant relationship with real gross domestic product in Nigeria. Credit to the private sector had an inverse and insignificant relationship with real gross domestic product in Nigeria. The error correction mechanism ECM (-) showed that there was a slow adjustment process in real gross domestic product since the speed of adjustment is approximately 39.1 per cent. The diagnostic test results confirmed the robustness of the model over time. Finally, the results of the Granger Causality test revealed a causality situation. With this, we can infer that those changes in money supply help to explain the changes in RGDP in Nigeria. The study recommends that Economic growth (RGDP) can be sustained if monetary policy is emphasized on both a short- and long-term basis.

Keywords: Real Gross Domestic Product, Money supply, Credit to Private Sector, and Total Government Expenditure.

I. INTRODUCTION

The relationship between money supply and economic growth has received more attention than any other subject matter in the field of monetary economics in recent years because of the importance of economic growth among the macroeconomic objectives of nations for both developed and developing (Ogunmuyiwa&Okone, 2010). Money supply is the total amount of all forms of money in circulation in a given country at a given period of time (Abdullahi, 2009). The Central Bank of Nigeria categorized the total money supply into two broad categories. These are near money (M1) and broad money (M2). M1 is the currency in circulation plus current account deposits with commercial banks, while M2 is M1 plus savings and time deposits (Gatawa, Abdulgafar, & Olarinde, 2017).

Economic growth, according to Jhingan (2003), is the process whereby the real per capita income of a country increases over a long period of time, and is measured by the increase in the amount of goods and services produced in a country. A growing economy produces more goods and services in each successive time period. Thus, in a wider perspective, it implies raising the standard of living of the people and reducing income inequality. In the words of Zhattau (2013), economic growth is the basis of increased prosperity, and it comes from the accumulation of more capital and innovations, which lead to technical progress, an idea similar to the Solow growth model, which sees economic growth in terms of growth in total GDP due to an increase in population, technical progress, and investment.

Growth according to Classical Economists signifies an increase in the rate of investment (Abdulsalam & Abdullahi, 2016). In other words, growth is a function of the share of profit in the national income. There exists a positive relationship between a higher rate of profit and a higher rate of growth in the long run.

Evidence in the Nigerian economy has shown that in the 1980s, a relationship exists between the stock of money and economic growth or economic activity. Over the years, Nigeria has been controlling its economy through variations in its stock of money. Consequent upon the effect of the collapse of oil prices in 1981 and the Balance of payment deficit experienced during this period, various methods of stabilization, ranging from fiscal to monetary policies, were used. Interest rates were fixed, and these were said to be beneficial to big borrower farmers (Ogunmuyiwa&Okone, 2010). Ikhide and Alawode (1993), while evaluating the effect of the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP), concluded that reducing money stock through increased interest rates would lower gross National product. Thus, the notion that the stock of money varies with economic activities applies to the Nigerian economy (Laidler 1993). The output development and other economic growth processes via interest rate deregulation in the Nigerian economy call for a considerable test of the validity of Friedman and Mieselman's (1963) work on the Nigerian economy, as reported by Ogunmuyiwa and Okone (2010). The implication of the stability of the relationship between money and economic growth was to show the effectiveness of monetary policy following the conventional Hicksian IS-LM analysis.

The overall objective of the study is to examine the nexus between money supply and economic growth in Nigeria.

The specific objectives of this study are to examine the relationship between:

1. money supply and real gross domestic product in Nigeria
2. credit to the private sector and real gross domestic product in Nigeria
3. government expenditure and real gross domestic product in Nigeria

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept Clarification

Concept of Money Supply

According to Jhingan (2003) and Abdullahi (2009), money supply is the total amount of all forms of money in circulation in a given country at a given period of time. Gatawa et al (2017) conceptually clarified that the total money supply can be grouped into two broad categories, namely: near money (M1) and broad money (M2). They added that M1 indicates currency in circulation plus current account deposits with commercial banks, while M2 is M1 plus savings and time deposits. Researchers have also made significant attempts to evaluate the interrelationships and causalities between bank credits to the private sector in general and the economic growth of specific countries and/or regions. Studies reveal that causalities could be uni-directional, bi-directional, and in some cases, indeterminate without significant long-run relationships. In this vein, Aliero, Abdullahi, and Adamu (2013) employed the autoregressive distributed lag bound approach (ARDL) in evaluating the relationship between banks' private sector credits and economic growth in Nigeria with time series data over 37 years (1974-2010). The study finds a significant long-run relationship between private sector credits and economic growth, but no significant causality between them in either direction. The study, therefore, concludes that Nigerian banks are playing neither supply-leading nor demand-following roles but conform to the Schumpeterian independent hypothesis stage. It recommends the implementation and adoption of more long-term loans for entrepreneurship ventures in Nigeria in place of the prevalence of present short-term and self-liquidating credit facilities preferred by Nigerian banks.

Fatoumata (2017) defined interest rate as the reward for not hoarding money. Over the years, interest rates have remained a subject for critical assessment with diverse implications for savings mobilization and investment promotion. Banks pay interest on deposits on the one hand and, on the other hand, they charge interest on loans and advances lent to borrowers. The difference between these two interest rates defines the interest spread, which constitutes a significant proportion of the profits of deposit money banks on economic growth.

Concept of Economic Growth

Economic growth, according to Jhingan (2003), is the process whereby the real per capita income of a country increases over a long period of time, and is measured by the increase in the amount of goods and services produced in a country. A growing economy produces more goods and services in each successive time period. Thus, in a wider perspective, it implies raising the standard of living of the people and reducing the inequality of income distribution. In the words of Zhattau (2013), economic growth is the basis of increased prosperity, and it comes from the accumulation of more capital and innovations, which lead to technical progress, an idea similar to the Solow growth model, which sees economic growth in terms of growth in total GDP due to an increase in population, technical progress, and investment. Growth, according to Classical Economists, signifies an increase in the rate of investment (Abdulsalam & Abdullahi, 2016). In other words, growth is a function of the share of profit in the national income. There exists a positive relationship between a higher rate of profit and a higher rate of growth in the long run. Economic growth is often measured by the increase in GDP (Owamah & Mgbomene, 2025; Owamah, 2025). A country is said to experience growth if its total output goes up over a certain time (Owamah & Mgbomene, 2025; Owamah et al., 2025).

Todaro (1985) defined economic growth as a long-term rise in capacity to supply increasingly diverse economic goods and services to its population; this growth capacity is based on advancing technologies, the institutional and ideological advancement that it demands. Economic growth occurs whenever there is a quantitative increase in a country's input and output over a period of time (Gatawa et al 2017).

Empirical Literature

Several studies have confirmed the significance of the money supply and economic growth in Nigeria. Ditimi et al (2018) empirically investigated the influence of money supply on inflation in Nigeria with the employment of the co-integration test and the error correction approach on annual time series data spanning from 1970 to 2016 to ascertain both the long-run and short-run dynamic relationship among the variables under consideration. Their findings showed that money supply does not considerably influence inflation, both in the long and short run, possibly because the country is in recession. The Granger causality outcome demonstrates that there is no causality between money supply and inflation in Nigeria within the study period and vice versa. Fitsum et al (2016) examined the relationship between inflation, money supply and economic growth in Ethiopia using cointegration and causality analysis and the results of the Johansen cointegration test revealed the presence of one cointegrating vector and the VECM demonstrated the existence of long run bi-directional causality between inflation and money supply and uni-directional causality from economic growth to inflation while in the short run one way causality were found from money supply and economic growth to inflation. They added that inflation is negatively and significantly affected by economic growth and recommended that combined efforts should be made by policymakers to increase the supply of output so as to reduce the prices of goods and services and boost the growth of the economy.

Iwedi (2016) examined the influence of money supply and government expenditure on Gross Domestic Product. He adopted the St Louis model on annual and quarterly time series data from 1960 to 1995. He finds money supply and export as being significant while examining the interaction between money and output in Nigeria between the periods 1960- 1995. The model assumed the irrelevance of anticipated monetary policy for short-run deviations of domestic output from its natural level. The result indicated that unanticipated growth in the money supply would have a positive effect on output. A clear examination of the above shows that there is no general agreement on the determinant of economic growth in the Nigerian economy.

Similarly, Adesoye (2012) examined the causality between price, monetary aggregate, and real output in Nigeria from the period 1970 to 2009 using the inflationary gap model that emanates from the quantity theory of money. The econometric findings suggested that the output gap was a strong indicator of controlling monetary aggregate in Nigeria, which indicates a positive impact of money supply on economic growth. Looking at the impact of injection and withdrawal of money stock on economic growth in Nigeria, Taiwo (2012) adopted Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) as an estimation technique over the period of (1970-2008). The results revealed that monetary aggregate injection has a

positive effect on economic growth, while withdrawal of money stock showed a negative impact on the GDP of Nigeria.

In a recent study by Chinwuba et al (2015) estimating a time series data covering a period of 1981-2008 with simple OLS on the Nigerian economy, the result suggests that money supply exerts a considerable positive impact on economic growth. An investigation into the long-run and short-run impact of money supply on economic growth of Nigeria for the period 1986-2006 by Omotor (2010) using VAR Model, the results provide evidence in support of the long-run positive impact of money supply on growth in income, but have no impact in the short-run. Adeyeye and Fajemibola (2006) empirically studied the impact of interest rate and money supply, proxied by bank loans, on the GDP. The result showed that although a bank loan is significant.

Gatawa et al (2017) study on the impact of money supply and inflation on economic growth in Nigeria from 1973-2013 using VAR Model and Granger Causality test within error correction framework revealed a positive impact of broad money supply, while inflation and interest rate hurt growth, most in the long run. The short-run parsimonious results revealed that, except for inflation, the broad money supply and interest rate were negatively related to economic growth, while the results of the causality tests revealed that none of the explanatory variables Granger-cause economic growth, implying that money supply, inflation, and interest rate have not influenced growth. The study, therefore, recommended an expansionary monetary policy, zero-interest-based finance capable of attracting investment in the real sector of the economy, and arresting the inflationary tendency associated with monetary policy.

Inam (2014) examined the role of money supply on economic growth in Nigeria between 1985 and 2012. Using the augmented Cobb-Douglas production function and relying on co-integration / Error Correction Methodology, it is found that the money supply not only has a positive impact on economic growth in Nigeria, but such impact is strongly and statistically significant. Others in Nigeria who have confirmed a strong relationship between money supply and growth include (Odedokun 1996; Owoye&Onafowora, 2007).

Oyeyemi and Awujola (2014) examined the impact of some determinants of economic growth on the Gross Domestic Product (GDP) using multiple regression methodology. These determinants include interest rate, inflation rate, oil revenue, federal government expenditure, money supply, foreign private investment, and foreign exchange rate. The study reveals that money supply, oil revenue, federal government expenditure, and foreign private investment had a significant impact on economic growth, while the inflation rate, interest rate, and foreign exchange rates adopted so far by the government do not have a significant impact on economic growth (GDP). The study recommended that the productive capacity should be improved by the government through direct investment in the real sectors of the economy, and government expenditure should be expanded on productive ventures since its impact on economic growth is positive.

El-seoud (2014) tested the relationship between money supply and GDP in Bahrain for the period of 13years. Using Cointegration, Error Correction model, and Granger causality techniques, the findings reveal the existence of a long-run equilibrium between real GDP and real money supply, while the Error term and F-test indicate unidirectional causality running from real GDP to real money supply in the short run as well as in the long run.

III. METHODOLOGY

Model Specification

Some aspects of this model were developed in the theoretical framework of the study. The model of Iwedi (2016), on which this work is mainly hinged, is presented as follows:

$$RGDP = f(M2) \tag{3.2}$$

$$RGDP = \beta_1 + \beta_2 M2 + \mu \tag{3.3}$$

Where: RGDP = Real Gross Domestic Product Growth Rate and M2 = Money Supply Growth Rate.

Other variables identified in the literature influencing economic growth apart from the ones included in Iwedi's work include Credit to Private Sector and Government Expenditure (GEX). These variables were included in the specification of the current study to capture the link between money supply and economic growth in Nigeria using RGDP as a proxy for economic growth.

The model for the current study is stated thus:

$$\ln\text{RGDP}_t = f(\text{M2}_t, \text{CPS}_t, \ln\text{GEXP}_t)$$

(3.4)

The linear relationship of equation (3.4) could be stated as:

$$\ln\text{RGDP}_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1\text{M2}_t + \beta_2\text{CPS}_t + \beta_3\ln\text{GEXP}_t + U_t \quad (3.5)$$

(Apriori expectation $\beta_1, \beta_2, \beta_3 > 0$)

Where: $\ln\text{RGDP}$ = log of Real Gross Domestic Product, $\ln\text{CPS}$ = log of Credit to Private Sector, $\ln\text{GEX}$ = log of Total Government Expenditure, U_t = Disturbance term or error term, β_0 = Intercept, $\beta_1 - \beta_3$ = Coefficient of the independent variables, and t is the time trend.

Sources of Data and Variables Description

Data for this study were obtained from secondary sources, which include the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2018), Academic Journals for various years, the National Bureau of Statistics, and various issues. Below are the variables sourced and used for this study:

Gross Domestic Product (GDP): This is the monetary value of goods and services produced in an economy during a period of time, irrespective of the nationality of the people who produced the goods and services. It is calculated without making deductions for depreciation.

GDP at Constant Basic Prices (otherwise known as the Real GDP) equals GDP at Constant Market Prices less indirect taxes net of subsidies (CBN, 2017).

Money Supply Growth Rate (M2): Money supply is the total amount of all forms of money in circulation in a given country at a given period of time. It is written as near money (M1) plus broad money (M2). M1 indicates the total currency in circulation plus current account deposits with commercial banks plus savings and time deposits (Iwedi, 2016).

Credit to Private Sector: This is the total credit given to private individuals, firms, and corporate bodies for investment purposes by deposit money banks at a given rate of interest. Bank credit is the credit facilities that banks give to their customers, investors, or others that meet the bank's requirements for such loans or overdrafts with a certain lending rate of interest charged for a specific period of time (Okosodo and Mamudu, 2018).

Government Expenditure (GEX): This is the total government spending on both recurrent and capital projects and programmes in Nigeria. Oyeyemi and Awujola (2014) reported that government expenditure improves the level of economic growth through policy implementation efforts, projects, and programmes.

Method of Data Analysis

The method used in analyzing the data collected for this research is basically descriptive and statistical in nature. Phillips-Perron statistic was employed to perform the stationarity test. Statistical theory requires that variables be stationary before the application of standard econometric techniques. This was done to avoid spurious (misleading) results. Granger Causality test was done to determine the causal relationship between money supply and economic growth in Nigeria. The Johansen cointegration test was also conducted to examine the existence or otherwise of a long-run relationship among the economic and selected financial deepening variables in the models. The error correction model was thereafter estimated to determine the speed of adjustment from short to long-run equilibrium. Diagnostic and stability tests were also conducted to confirm the robustness of the model.

IV. ANALYSIS OF DATA AND INTERPRETATION OF REGRESSION RESULTS

Unit Root Test

The stationarity status of the economic and selected financial deepening indicators was examined using the Phillips-Perron test statistic. The results, which are displayed in Table 4.1 below, show that all the selected variables (Gross Domestic Product (GDP), Money supply (M2), Credit to Private Sector (CPS), and Total Government Expenditure (GEX) were stationary at first difference. In other words, GDP, M2, CPS, and GEX were found to be stationary at I (1).

Table 4.1: Unit Root Test Results

Variable	Level	First Difference	Order of Integration
RGDP	6.954950 (1.0000)	-5.86320 (0.0004)	I (1)
M2	4.450967 (1.0000)	-3.713514 (0.0082)	I (1)
CPS	2.716700 (1.0000)	-4.879217 (0.0003)	I (1)
GEX	0.10247 (0.9616)	-7.681530 (0.0000)	I (1)
5%CV	2.945842	2.948404	

Source: Author’s compilation with information from stationarity test results

Note: i. Pro-value is reported in parenthesis.

ii. The Phillips-Perron test statistics were compared to 5 per cent critical value (C.V).

Cointegration Test using the Johansen Methodology

The results of the Unrestricted Cointegration Rank tests for the model are presented in Table 4.2. Starting with the null hypothesis that there are no cointegrating vector in the model, the results show that there exists at least three (3) cointegrating relationship in the model as both the Trace and Max-Eigen statistics rejected the null against the alternative at 5 per cent level of significance which shows that there is a unique long run relationship between money supply, credit to private sector, total government expenditure and gross domestic product in Nigeria.

Table 4.2.2: Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test result for the model

Hypothesised No. of CE(s)	Trace Stat.	Critical Value (0.05)	Prob**	Hypothesised No. of CE(s)	Max-Eigen Stat.	Critical Value (0.05)	Prob**
None *	154.8191	47.85613	0.0000	None *	72.44314	27.58434	0.0000
At most 1 *	82.37597	29.79707	0.0000	At most 1 *	59.94080	21.13162	0.0000
At most 2 *	22.43517	15.49471	0.0038	At most 2 *	19.58230	14.26460	0.0066
At most 3	2.852863	3.841466	0.0912	At most 3	2.852863	3.841466	0.0912

Source: Author’s compilation with information from unrestricted cointegration rank results.

Note: Both Trace and Max-Eigenvalue tests indicate 3 cointegrating equations at the 0.05 level, respectively. * denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level. ** Mackinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values.

Error Correction Representation (Short-run)

Table 4.3: Error Correction Representation of the Model

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
C	1001.277	531.2030	1.884923	0.0688
D(M2)	3.949627	0.882632	4.474827	0.0001
D(CPS)	-1.174026	0.754644	-1.555735	0.1299
D(GEX)	6.915710	2.949112	2.345014	0.0256
ECM (-1)	-0.391143	0.149517	-2.616047	0.0136

Source: Author’s compilation with information from ECM results.

Table 4.3 reports the results of the short-run error correction model. The result showed that money supply (M2) has a direct and significant relationship with real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria. This finding supports the work of Owoye and Onafowora (2007), Inam (2014), and Oyeyemi and Awujola (2014). Interestingly, a unit change in the money supply in Nigeria increases real gross domestic product by 3.949627.

The results also showed that credit to the private sector (CPS) has an inverse and insignificant relationship with real gross domestic product (RGDP) in Nigeria. A unit change in credit to the private sector in Nigeria reduces real gross domestic product by 1.174026 per cent.

The coefficient of government expenditure (GEX) is 6.915710. This implies that there is a direct relationship between government expenditure and real gross domestic product in Nigeria, and a 1 per cent change in government expenditure raised real gross domestic product by 6.915710 per cent. This result is consistent with previous studies of (Oyeyemi &Awujola, 2014).

Finally, the error correction mechanism $ecm(-)$ which is 0.391143 is statistically significant and has the appropriate sign (negative). It suggests, however, that there is a low adjustment process in real gross domestic product since the speed of adjustment is approximately 39.1 per cent. It is also a confirmation that money supply, credit to the private sector, total government expenditure, and real gross domestic product are cointegrated.

Diagnostic Test

To confirm the robustness of the model, a diagnostic test was performed as shown in Table 4.4.

Table 4.4: Key Regression and Diagnostic Statistics for the Model

R-squared	0.581684	Mean dependent var	3154.633
Adjusted R-squared	0.527708	S.D. dependent var	3627.254
S.E. of regression	2492.776	Akaike info criterion	18.60843
Sum squared resid	1.93E+08	Schwarz criterion	18.82836
Log likelihood	-329.9517	Hannan-Quinn criter.	18.68519
F-statistic	10.77667	Durbin-Watson stat	1.869010
Prob(F-statistics)	0.000014		

Source: Author’s compilation with information from ECM results

The coefficient of determination R^2 indicates that 58.2 per cent of the total variation of gross domestic product is jointly explained by money supply, credit to the private sector, and government expenditure. The Akaike information criterion, Schwarz criterion, and Hannan-Quinn criterion showed that the model is correctly specified. F statistic measuring the joint significance of all regressors in the model is statistically significant at the 5 per cent level. Similarly, the Durbin-Watson statistic of 1.869010 confirms that the autocorrelation problem is eliminated.

Stability Test

The stability test was conducted using the cumulative sum (CUSUM) of recursive residuals as shown in Figure 4.2. The existence of parameter instability is established if the cumulative sum of the squares of the residual goes outside the area between the critical (straight, bounded upper and lower) lines. From Figure 4.2, it was observed that the CUSUM at the 5 per cent significance level was stable over time because the observed bound lay between the upper and lower limits. In conclusion, at a 5 per cent critical value, the cumulative sum of recursive residuals is sufficient to explain the stability of the data over time.

Fig.4.2: Plot of Cumulative Sum of Recursive Residuals

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

This study aims to examine the link between money supply and economic growth in Nigeria. Gross Domestic Product is influenced by several factors, which include money supply, credit to the private sector, and total government expenditure, amongst others, which were reviewed under conceptual, theoretical, and empirical literature. However, there have been various debates on the impact of these variables on gross domestic products in Nigeria. Hence, the main objective is to examine the nexus

between Money supply and economic growth in Nigeria. Annual time series data from 1981 to 2018 on Gross Domestic Product (GDP), money supply, credit to the private sector, and total government expenditure used in this work were obtained mainly from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin (2018).

The study used log linear modeling specification before testing the stationarity status of the selected variables using the Phillips-Perron test statistic. The Johansen Cointegration test was also carried out to determine the existence or otherwise of a long-run relationship between economic and selected financial deepening indicators in Nigeria.

Finally, the Error Correction Mechanism was thereafter estimated to determine the speed of adjustment to long-run equilibrium. Diagnostic and stability tests were also conducted using the cumulative sum (CUSUM) of recursive residuals to confirm the robustness and stability of the model over time.

The empirical study aims to examine the nexus between money supply and economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2018. The Phillips-Perron test statistic results showed that the economic and selected financial deepening variables (gross domestic product, money supply, credit to private sector, and total government expenditure) were stationary at first difference. In other words, GDP, M2, CPS, and GEX were found to be stationary at I(1).

The Johansen cointegration test result indicates a long-run relationship between money supply, credit to the private sector, total government expenditure, and gross domestic product in Nigeria. On causality, there is a causality running from M2 to GDP and not vice versa. This shows that there is unidirectional causality from money supply (M2) to GDP in Nigeria during the period of study.

The empirical short-run results of the model revealed that money supply, credit to the private sector, and government expenditure were found to have a direct and significant relationship with gross domestic product in Nigeria.

The error correction mechanism (ECM) revealed a high adjustment process of the selected economic and financial deepening indicators on gross domestic product in Nigeria, as the speed of adjustment to the long-run equilibrium relationship is approximately 68.3 per cent. The diagnostic and stability tests conducted showed that the models have been stable over time.

Based on the conclusion, the following recommendations are made:

1. Economic growth (RGDP) can be sustained if monetary policy on the money supply is emphasized in both the short and long run by Nigeria's monetary authorities.
2. Central Bank of Nigeria should maintain and enhance the policies on credit to the private sector. This will promote and further develop the financial sector, especially in the lending rate to investors, so as to encourage investors to borrow more for investment purposes in Nigeria.
3. The monetary policy should be broader in definition to influence the effect of credit to the private sector and government expenditure on the components of aggregate demand. Hence, it will help to address the nexus between money supply and economic growth in Nigeria.
4. Government should ensure that 60% of its total expenditure is spent on capital or / infrastructural projects that will further increase economic growth significantly and, in return, boost the real gross domestic product in Nigeria.

REFERENCES

- Abbas, K. (1991). Causality Test between Money and Income: A Case Study of Selected Developing Asian Countries (1960- 1988). *The Pakistan Development Review*, (30).
- Abdullahi, H. (2009). *Monetary Economics: Theory, policy and the millennium global financial crisis: A Guide to Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria* (1st ed.). Halygraph Nig. Ltd. Minna and Kaduna.
- Abdulsalam, S.A. and Abdullahi, B. (2016). The Impact of Unemployment and inflation on Economic Growth in Nigeria from 1981 – 2014. *International Journal of Business and Economic Sciences Applied Research*, 9(1): 47-55. Retrieved online 28th June, 2018 at <http://ijbesar.teiemt.gr>
- Adesoye, A.B. (2012). Price, money and output in Nigeria: A co integration-causality analysis. *African Journal of Scientific Research*, 8(1): 428-442.

- Adeyeye, P.O. and Fajemibola, O.D. (2006). An Empirical Study of Interest Rate Policy on Economic Growth in Nigeria (1970-2007). *Business and Finance Herald*, 2(1): 225-251.
- Aliero, H.M., Abdullahi, Y.Z. and Adamu, N. (2013). Private Sector Credit and Economic Growth Nexus in Nigeria: An Autoregressive Distributed Lag Bound Approach. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(1).
- Amassona, D.; Nwosa, P.I. and Olaiya, S.A. (2011). An appraisal of monetary policy and its effect on macroeconomic stabilization in Nigeria. *Journal of Emerging Trends in Economics and Management Sciences*, 2(3): 232-237.
- Asogu, J.O. (1998). The Influence of Money Supply and Government Expenditure on Gross Domestic Product reported by Iwedi, M. (2016). The Link between Money Supply and Economic Growth in Nigeria: An Econometric Investigation. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 2(3): 42-51.
- CBN (2017). Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin Volume 28, December.
- CBN, (2018). Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin, Abuja, Volume 29, December.
- Chinwuba, O.; Akhor, S.O. and Akwaden, S.T. (2015). Monetary policy innovations and growth rate of output in Nigeria. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 1(4): 1-15.
- Cooper and Fraser, (1990) reported by Iwedi, M. (2016). The Link between Money Supply and Economic Growth in Nigeria: An Econometric Investigation. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 2(3): 42-51.
- Ditimi, A.; Keji, S. and Emma-Ebere, O. (2018). The influence of money supply on inflation in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Management*, 31(1): 5-23.
- Eita, J. and Ashipala, J. (2010). Determinants of Unemployment in Namibia. *International Journal of Business and Management*, 5(10): 92-104.
- El.seoud, M.S.A. (2014). Testing the Relationship between Money Supply and GDP in Bahrain. *International Journal of Economics, Commerce and Management United Kingdom*, 1(5): 1-16.
- Essien, A.E. (2001). Nigeria's Economic Growth: performance and determinants. *Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and financial Review*, 40(3): 16-39.
- Ezirim, B. (2005). *Finance dynamics: Principles, applications and techniques*. Port Harcourt: Markowitz Centre for Research and Development.
- Fatoumata, K.M. (2017). Impact of Interest Rate on Economic Growth in Nigeria. *Pyrex Journal of Business and Finance Management Research*, 3(3): 98-111.
- Fisher, I. (1911), *The Purchasing Power of Money: Its Determination and Relation to Credit, Interest and Crises*, Macmillan, New York.
- Fitsum, S.D; Yilkal, W.A. and Teshome, A.R. (2016). The Relationship between Inflation, Money Supply and Economic Growth in Ethiopia: Co integration and Causality Analysis. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 6(1): 556-565.
- Friedman, M. (1969), *The Optimum Quantity of Money*, Macmillan.
- Friedman, M. and Meiselman, D. (1963). *The Relative Stability of Monetary Velocity and the Investment Multiplier*, Ed. Commission on Money and Credit, in *stabilization Policies*, Englewood Cliffs, N. J.: Prentice-Hall.
- Gatawa, N.M; Abdulgafar, A. and Olarinde, M.O. (2017). Impact of Money Supply and Inflation on Economic Growth in Nigeria (1973-2013). *Journal of Economics and Finance*, 8(3): 26-37.
- Hosseini, A. (2005). Granger-Causality between Inflation, Money Growth, Currency Devaluation and Economic Growth, *International Journal of Applied Econometrics and Quantitative Studies*, 2(3).
- Hussain, F. and Abbas, K. (2000). Money, Income, Prices, and Causality in Pakistan: A Trivariate Analysis. *The Pakistan Development Review*, 178.
- Ikhide, S.I. and Alawode, A.A. (1993). Financial Sector Reforms, Macroeconomic Instability and the Order of Economic Liberalization: Evidence from Nigeria. *AERC Workshop Paper*, Nairobi. May 28-June 4.
- Inam, U. (2014). Money Supply and Economic Growth in Nigeria: An Econometric Analysis (1985-2011). *Journal of Economics and Sustainable Development*, 5(12):149-155.

- Isiaka, S.B.; Abdulraheem, A. and Mustapha, I.Y. (2011). Impact of fiscal and monetary policy on the Level of economic activities in Nigeria. *Lapai Journal of management Sciences*, 1(2): 1-22.
- Iwedi, M. (2016). The Link between Money Supply and Economic Growth in Nigeria: An Econometric Investigation. *International Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 2(3): 42-51.
- Jhingan, M.L. (2003). *Advanced Macroeconomic Theory 11h Edition*. Delhi: Vrinda Publications (P) LTD.
- Keynes, J.M. (1936). *The General Theory of Employment, Interest and Money*, Macmillan, London.
- Laider, D.E.W. (1993). *The Demand for Money: Theories, Evidence and Problems*. 4th Edition, New York: Harper Collins.
- Lucas, R. (1988). On the Mechanics of Economic Development. *Journal of Monetary Economics*, 22(1): 3–42.
- Masha, I. (2002). The Dynamics of Money, Output and Prices in Nigeria: Some Neutrality propositionals using the Vector Error Correction Specification. *Central Bank of Nigeria Economic and Financial Review*, 40(2): 29-59.
- Mbongo, J.E.; Mutasa, F. and Msigwa, R.E. (2014). The effects of money supply on inflation in Tanzania. *Economics*, 3(2): 19-26.
- Murty, K.S.; Sailaja, K. and Demissie, W.M. (2012). The Long Run Impact of Bank Credit on Economic Growth in Ethiopia: Evidence from Johansen’s Multivariate Co-Integration Approach. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 4(14).
- Nuno, C.L. (2012). Bank Credit and Economic Growth: A dynamic Panel Data Analysis. *The Economic Research Guardian*, 2(2).
- Obaid, G. (2007). *Money Supply-Output Causality in Egypt*, Faculty of Commercial and Business Administration Magazine, Helwan University.
- Odedokun (1996). Alternative Economic Approaches for Analyzing the Role of the Financial Sector in Economic Growth. Time Series Evidence from LDC’s. *Journal of Development Economics*, 50(1).
- Ogunmuyiwa, M. and Ekone, F. (2010). Money Supply- Economic Growth Nexus in Nigeria. *Journal of Olabisi Onabanjo University*, 22(3).
- Okosodo, L.A. and Mamudu, Z.U. (2018). Empirical Investigation of the Impact of Deposit Money Banks Credit on Investment in Nigeria. *The Nigerian Journal of Economic and Management Studies*, 7(1): 246-278.
- Omeke, P.C. and C.U. Ugwunyi, (2010). Money, Price and Output: A Causality Test for Nigeria. *American Journal of Scientific Research*, 8(1): 78-87.
- Omotor, D.G. (2010). The Nigerian Economy and Monetary Policy: Some Simple Empirics. MPRA Paper No. 22672: 1-27.
- Owamah, E. K., & Mgbomene, C. (2025). Exchange rate and Nigerian’s economic performance. *Jalingo Journal of Social and Management Sciences*, 6(4), 287–298.
- Owamah, E. K., & Mgbomene, C. (2025). Impact of oil and non-oil exports on Nigeria’s economic growth. *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 8(7), 4892– 4902. <https://doi.org/10.47191/jefms/v8-i7-75>
- Owamah, E. K., Egbon, P. C., & Ishioro, B. O. (2025). Remittances and income inequality in selected countries in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). *Journal of Economics, Finance and Management Studies*, 8(10), 6832–6844. <https://doi.org/10.47191/jefms/v8-i10-27>
- Owamah, E. K. (2025). The dominant impact of oil exports on economic growth in Nigeria: A comparative ARDL analysis with non-oil exports. *Journal of Economics, Business, and Commerce*, 2(2), 207–215. <https://doi.org/10.69739/jebc.v2i2.1082>
- Owoye, O. and Onafowora, A.O. (2007). M2 Targeting, Money Demand and Real GDP Growth in Nigeria: Do Rules Apply? *Journal of Business and Public Affairs*, 1(2): 25-34.
- Oyeyemi, A.O. and Awujola, A. (2014). An Appraisal of Some Factors Influencing Economic Growth in Nigeria. *International Journal of African and Asian Studies - An Open Access International Journal*, (3): 33-39.
- Pigou. A.C. (1917). The Value of Money. *The Quarterly Journal of Economics*, 32.